

Inter-territorial Association of Wild Mushroom Harvesting Professionals

Introduction

Go Mikogest states that it is crucial to use the sectorial associationism as a tool to professionalize the primary sector of the mycological activity. With the growing activity of collecting and marketing mushrooms, most regional administrations have independently regulated their mycological exploitation. This lack of legislative homogeneity in the territory causes difficulties in the management of the mycological resource, among which the following have been detected: (i) Lack of coordination between the different sectors concerned. (ii) Lack of knowledge of mycological production in the territory, as well as its local economic impact. It is precisely the local collectors who obtain a large part of the mycological resource for subsequent sale. However, the lack of professionalism in this sector, most of them being sporadic collectors, forces a dispersion of the resource to other sales channels, making it very difficult to quantify collection data in producing areas.

Approach and main results

GO Mikogest's proposal to face the problem of the lack of professionalism in this sector has been the creation and promotion of the Inter-territorial Association of Wild Mushroom Harvesting Professionals. The association's statutes have been drafted for their subsequent registration and constitution, accompanying these actions with the development of a training plan aimed at the professional collector. Thus, with the creation of this national professional association, it is intended to: (i) Achieve the professionalization of the group of collectors. (ii) To provide the necessary training for the unequivocal identification of edible species. (iii) To ensure the conservation of all mycological species. (iv) To prevent indiscriminate collection by people outside the municipality or locality. (v) To avoid the loss of the usual local collector. The association develops its activities throughout the Spanish territory, represents the wild mushroom collecting sector, and arises to defend and promote the economic and social interests that are proper to this activity, both in its individual and collective development. Membership is open to all individuals who hold the status of professional wild mushroom picker

Lessons learned

To ensure the success of a partnership, in addition to encouraging its establishment, it is essential to have a period of accompaniment, which can last one or two years. This will allow the initiative to move beyond the initial start-up phase and give it a better chance of success.

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

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